

COMBATING INSECURITY IN NIGERIA: AN APPRAISAL OF EXISTING AND SUGGESTED COMPLEMENTARY APPROACHES

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ABSTRACT

The government has adopted various approaches toward resolving the challenge of insecurity in Nigeria. This paper aims to assess the strengths and weaknesses of the existing approaches to suggest other complementary approaches that can be adopted by policymakers to halt the menace. The paper adopted a qualitative approach as well as the descriptive method of research. The paper established that various administrations in Nigeria have implemented various approaches including the Economic Explanation Approach, Military Approach as well as Amnesty or “Carrot” Approach, among others, combating insecurity. Considering the weaknesses of the existing approaches, the paper recommended that Guantanamo Bay Detention Camp Approach, the America-Mexico Border Wall Approach, the China Population Growth Control Approach and the Compulsory and Free Education Approach be made complementary to tackle the security drift. The paper acknowledged that although some of the suggested approaches may be financially costly, it is however worth embarking upon in the interest of the citizens and the survival of the country.

KEYWORDS: Amnesty, armed-conflict, de-radicalisation, insecurity, insurgency, terrorism.

INTRODUCTION

Apart from the Biafran secessionist war, insurgency has come to become the greatest challenge to Nigeria's corporate existence since independence in 1960. The perennial communal land and ethnic clashes of the colonial and post-independence era have now plummeted into insignificance in the face of the post-military constant and widespread ferocious attacks on ordinary innocent citizens and security forces by bandits, kidnappers and terrorists. This has brought Nigeria to the notoriety of being regarded as a country under siege

by terrorists and criminals. Its negative effect on the economy, governance and society has been colossal. Industries have closed down, forms have been abandoned, the transportation sector has become unsafe for commuters, unemployment and criminality have soared, foreign companies have relocated from Nigeria, government revenue has dwindled, Nigeria's diplomatic regard among the comity of nations has plummeted, among others (Ita & Bassey, 2022; Atai & Esetang, 2024).

Scholars and other citizens have expressed serious concern about the high insecurity level in Nigeria. As usual, in such situations, varied explanations and solutions have been bandied on how to arrest the ugly situation. A review of some of their postulations shows that they are mostly old approaches such as economic, military and appeasement approaches to explain the problem. Since the role of theory, among other things, is to explain, predict and control societal phenomena (Ndiyo, 2005), therefore wrong diagnosis would result in wrong solutions. That, perhaps, explains why various solutions adopted so far by various administrations since 2009 have failed to stem the upsurge of insecurity in Nigeria. For example, massive equipment and personnel build-up of the military and their deployment against terrorism, the arrest, killings and decimation of terrorist groups, starving of terrorist enclaves of basic means of survival such as food, fuel and weapons as well as constant bombardment of their locations from the air have not reduced their lethality. As contended by Esetang & Atai (2023), the existing theoretical foundations powering the government's ongoing counter-insurgency approaches which are mainly focusing on the improvement of the economy to create jobs and reduce unemployment among the youths, massive military combat against the terrorists and their appeasement through amnesty programme have not worked to reduce insecurity in Nigeria.

This paper has as its focus the assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of the existing approaches in order to explain the persistence of insecurity in Nigeria. Leveraging on the weaknesses identified, the paper intends to suggest other complementary approaches that can be adopted by the government to halt the security drift in the country.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Insecurity

To understand the concept of insecurity, it is imperative to know the meaning of security. From the standpoint of the United Nations Development Programme (1994) security is the ability to defend against harmful and covert disturbances to day-to-day activity at homes, workplaces, communities, etc. This suggests that guaranteeing the safety of people and property is a part of security. Williams (2008) viewed security from a socio-political perspective. In the author's opinion, security is inherently socio-political as it is necessary for political stability and, in turn, for social activities to function normally.

Onifade (2013) conceived security as a situation that emerges from the establishment of ways of protecting individuals, information, and properties from hostile people, influences, and behaviour. It has to do with a situation in which people can travel around within a given natural space or elsewhere without any real and imaginary threats to their lives or properties. A condition where, with their two eyes firmly closed, people will sleep at night.

Flowing from above elucidations, the term "insecurity" is the opposite of security. According to Beland (2005), it denotes peril, uncertainty, danger, and a lack of safety and protection. It implies the state of fear or anxiety stemming from a concrete or alleged lack of

protection. That means that there is insufficient or no freedom from risk and suggests the absence of security, peace, and order. For Achumba *et al.* (2013) insecurity can be perceived from two angles. First, as a state of being exposed to danger or the fear of it, whereas danger is the state of being vulnerable to damage or injury. Second, feeling insecure is the same as being exposed to danger or anxiety, with anxiety being a generalised uncomfortable feeling that is felt when one anticipates some sort of mishap. These explanations of insecurity highlight a crucial point: people who experience insecurity are not only unsure of what could happen or oblivious of it when it does, but they are also more susceptible to threats and hazards when they materialise.

For Ajodo-Adebanjoko & Ugwuoke (2014), insecurity refers to the state of being vulnerable to terror, danger, risk, molestation, bullying, harassment, etc. in all aspects. For example, insecurity might be understood as a danger to the state, which frequently explained the arms race and the development of nuclear weapons. Under this condition, it becomes difficult for individuals within a State to engage in productive activities. Unarguably, without security, the state is bound to witness great difficulty in connecting its human development and the promotion of the general well-being of the people.

According to Zubairu (2020), insecurity is a mental state marked by vulnerability and self-doubt as well as the condition of being unsafe or insecure. Anything from early life experiences to upsetting circumstances, maltreatment, and personal anxieties might cause it. It's possible that security awareness and observable objective security are not well mapped. For instance, compared to the terror of Boko-Haram, there is reportedly less fear of kidnappers along the Kaduna-Abuja road and in other northern regions. The author reasoned that the very existence of security guards serves as protection. For example, the security personnel stationed along the Kaduna-Abuja road and in other parts of the north, particularly the northeast, may cause mutual interference or even neutralise the effects of insecurity issues; however, the general public still perceives the security personnel as taking proactive steps to stop the acts.

Existing Government Approaches to Combating Insecurity in Nigeria

In contemporary period, the Nigerian government have adopted a number of approaches in combating insecurity in the country, prominently among them: the economic approach, military approach and amnesty or appeasement approach. These are examined hereunder:

(i) Economic Approach: Proponents of economic explanation of insecurity are of the view that insecurity is caused by such economic issues as unemployment among the youth population, poverty among the people and general inequality in the Nigerian society (Todaro & Smith, 2011). Leveraging on Conflict Theory, first credited to Karl Marx and later promoted by Max Weber, Charles Wright Mills and George William Domhoff, the paper's position is that competition for scarce economic resources keeps society in a state of perpetual conflict, with the intensity of the competition varying from peaceful expression of discontent to open-armed combat such as terrorism.

Due to the unequal distribution of resources in society, the elites who are lucky enough to possess positions of privilege, employment, wealth, and power attempt to hang onto them by any means necessary, usually by using force and deceit, while simultaneously oppressing the underprivileged and jobless. They bolster their own social supremacy by reserving certain posts for their cronies and blood relatives, therefore keeping the marginalised groups from

even attempting to survive economically. It becomes obvious, therefore, that rivalry for limited economic resources in the fields of job development, employment generation, poverty reduction, and enhancing equality among the people is the fundamental root of war and terrorism.

The implication of this approach in terms of solution is that conflict and insecurity can only be curbed if the marginal groups such as the poor, unemployed and the less privilege people are allowed access to economic and political power as enjoyed by the elite group. Indeed, Kashim Shettima, the former government of Borno State and the current vice president of Nigeria once affirmed that, “Once we engage our youths, once we create jobs, this nihilism, this madness will evaporate. . . , the solution to Boko Haram for us in northern Nigeria is agriculture”. He stressed that massive development of agriculture to engage youths could not only end insurgency in the North-east but could provide jobs to other citizens to make crime unattractive (Akowe, 2014, p. 59). Similarly, Ojo (2018, p. 22) averred that worsening poverty and unemployment is caused by Nigeria's bad economy which he dubbed “the headquarters of poverty”. For him, increase in unemployment is fuelled by insecurity. Hence, for insecurity menace to be solved, government must tackle poverty and unemployment in Nigeria.

Indeed, the country is plagued by chronic youth unemployment, which is likely to continue in ascendancy as thousands of graduates are produced annually without jobs available for the majority of them. Ita & Basse (2022, p. 2) amplified this viewpoint in a claim that “in Nigeria unemployment has become one of the most serious socio-economic problems”. As the number of young people without jobs rises, there is a likelihood that these individuals may turn their energy towards illegal activities, which will raise the nation's crime and criminality rates. If adopted exclusively, the economic approach for tackling insecurity, which includes creating jobs for the majority of residents and reducing poverty, might not be sufficient to stem the menace.

(ii) Military Approach to Insecurity: Military approach to insecurity is premised on the Realist Theory. Realists hold the following basic ideas and assumptions about security: They hold national security and state survival highly, believe that war is the final means of resolving problems, have a gloomy view of human nature, and believe that progress can only be achieved in domestic political life (Jackson & Sorensen, 2003; Atai & Ita, 2021).

Although a country is expected to secure itself by building up its military forces with sophisticated weapons and trained personnel, however, massive acquisition of state-of-the-art weapons and equipment especially during the tenure of Muhammadu Buhari presidency was propelled by realist principle of eternal inviolability of the values, integrity and sovereignty of the state. Thus, such all-out military campaigns as “Operation Lafiya Dole” for North-east, “Operation Hadarin Daji” for the North-west, and Egwueke 1, 2, 3 for the South-east among others, are examples of efforts to adopt a military approach to insecurity (Tunoh, 2021). Although, through military action, the government was able to regain territories earlier controlled by terrorists in the northeast, however, the military has only won the battle and not the war as terrorists who escaped military bombardments fled to hitherto secured areas of the northwest. The entire northern zones are today experiencing insecurity. Military approach may not therefore provide a valid solution to the insecurity menace in Nigeria.

(iii) Amnesty or “Carrot” Approach to Insecurity: This approach is an aspect of the doctrine of appeasement of the enemy. Appeasement, according to Kegley & Blanton (2011,

p. 75) is a strategy of making concessions to a belligerent in the hope that, satisfied, it will not make additional claims. As posited by Omotoso (2017), the strategy was first introduced in Nigeria by the Umaru Yar'Adua's administration to rein the Niger Delta militants, and was subsequently adopted by the military as a strategy to curb insecurity in the north. On June 25, 2009, the late former President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Musa Yar'Adua, exercised his constitutional authority under Section 175 of the Federal Republic of Nigeria's constitution and pardoned the insurgents from the Niger Delta unconditionally. The militants had to give up all of their weapons and ammunition and publicly repudiate militancy in order for the pardon to take effect, which lasted for 60 days from June 25 to October 4, 2009.

As asserted by Raji & Yusuf (2024), prior to the amnesty era, there were more than 10 militant organisations in the region, some of which are: Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), Federated Niger Delta Ijaw Communities (FNDIC), General "Boyloaf", Outlaws, Niger Delta Strike Force (NDSF), Niger Delta People's Volunteer Force (NDPVF), Niger Delta Vigilantes (NDV) and People's Liberation Force (PLF). These insurgents comprised of both individuals and groups, each with a different motivation for attacking the governments and the international oil companies. For instance, between 2006 and 2009, after the decline of the Niger Delta People's Volunteer Force (NDPVF), the most active militant group was the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND). MEND is an umbrella organisation whose political objectives have focused on demanding increased political participation, a greater share of the profits derived from local oil and gas, socio-economic development, and the reduced militarization of the region. The group has made use of kidnapping and car bombing with the aim of kidnapping of foreign oil workers, attacks against oil pipelines, and oil bunkering.

The amnesty programme involves granting pardon to bandits, terrorists and kidnappers who lay down their arms and renounce violence to be dubbed "repentant terrorists". After making them to pass through a period of de-radicalisation programme, they are released into the society. The amnesty initiative was divided into three stages: the demobilisation and disarmament of militants, the integration and rehabilitation of former militants, and the post-amnesty package, which includes significant infrastructure development. The disarmed militants were promised a monthly salary of N65,000 (about \$407), rent payment, and vocational training (Ibaba, 2011; Oluwaniyi, 2011).

According to Austine & Sunday (2013), several militants surrendered several weapons and ammunition during the first phase. It was noted that approximately 26,358 former militants accepted the offer of amnesty (20,192 in the first phase, representing those who accepted the offer on or before October 4, 2009, and 6,616 in the second phase, which took place in November 2010, representing those who accepted the offer after October 4, 2009). As a result, there did not seem to be as many conflicts or as many militants acquiring and entering the area with weapons.

For the second stage, which was designed to satisfy the ex-militant's training requirements, some rehabilitation facilities were made available (Ajodo-Adebanjoko, 2017). Due to the limited capacity of the centres to house a large number of registered ex-militants, the trainings were conducted in batches. Each batch of ex-militants was scheduled to spend four weeks in the rehabilitation programme, which included reorientation, therapy, and moral and spiritual renewal. According to a survey on the career goals of ex-militants, they have a strong preference for ten (10) industries, including oil and gas, maritime services, fabrication

and welding technology, exploration and production, and processing engineering. The training programmes in these industries were expected to last anywhere from three to eighteen months (Akinwale, 2010). Under this scheme, those who choose to return to school for additional education were also offered the chance. Although many terrorists embraced the programme, it has not impacted significantly in reducing the incidence of terrorism, banditry and kidnapping in Nigeria. Indeed, the report holds that some of the rehabilitated repentant terrorists may have re-joined the murderous gang (Idowu, 2018).

Strengths and Weaknesses of Government Approaches towards Combating Insecurity in Nigeria

The afore-discussed three approaches have, in some way, confronted the discontents and grievances of the youths who are the main purveyors of terrorism in Nigeria. For example, in pursuit of economic solution to insecurity, the Buhari administration established National Social Investment Programme (NSIP) in which billions of naira was invested to create jobs and generate employment for the youths. Moreover, through N-power, Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP) and Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (HGSFP), thousands of youths were gainfully engaged. Also, National Directorate of Employment (NDE) trained thousands of youths on various skills and empowered them with start-up loans and starter packs. The Federal government also banned the importation of certain food items in order to encourage youths to engage themselves in agricultural ventures by making loans available to them. All these efforts have not reduced the intensity of insecurity in Nigeria.

Similarly, military approach succeeded marginally, as terrorists fleeing military assault have spread to new areas which initially did not witness insecurity, for example the North-western zone. This partly explains why Zamfara State is regarded the centre of banditry in the North-western zone (Omeihe, 2018).

Lastly, the amnesty or appeasement programme aimed at encouraging terrorists to lay down their weapons and embrace the amnesty programme has not been embraced by all the insurgent groups. For instance, the cut to the programme funding in 2015, along with the government's failure to improve the socio-economic conditions in the Delta region, and actions by security guards of oil installations, led to a new insurgency in 2016 and to the emergence of several militant groups, in particular of the Niger Delta Avengers (NDA). NDA is currently active in the Niger Delta. Although it shares the same objectives as MEND, it distances itself from the latter and calls for the autonomy of the region. In 2016, the group launched a large number of attacks on oil infrastructures. The tactics of the NDA mainly focus on attacks on oil and gas installations. This partially explains the failure of Amnesty or the "Carrot" Approach and the persistence of insecurity in all parts of Nigeria.

Suggested Complementary Approaches for Combating Insecurity in Nigeria

From the preceding analysis, it is clear that present theoretical approaches being adopted by the government to combat insecurity have not so far significantly worked to stem insecurity in Nigeria. They have to be complemented by other pragmatic approaches to ensure success in the war. Thus, the following are suggested for dealing with the insecurity situation in Nigeria:

(I) Guantanamo Bay Detention Camp Approach: Guantanamo Bay detention Camp (Gitmo) located at the United States Naval Base in Southern Cuba was put up in 2002

following the 9/11 2001 terrorist attack on the World Trade Centre in the United States, to house Muslim militants and suspected terrorists captured by the United States military forces in Afghanistan, Iraq, Syria among others. In the camp, the suspected terrorists were subjected to intense measures such as indefinite detention without trial, interrogation and solitary confinement (Egbo, 2001). If the United States, the epitome of democracy in the world, could take such extreme extra-democratic measures to confront terrorist threats to their country, Nigeria should not hesitate to do the same. In Nigeria, such facilities should be established in off-shore locations and build specifically for maximum security and zero access to unauthorized persons (Atai & Ita, 2021; Ita, 2022). All arrested Boko Haram terrorists, bandits, kidnapers, water pirates and crude oil thieves should be detained in such facility.

This approach is suggested owing to the growing disappointment by many Nigerians over the failure of Nigeria's democratic process to arrest the ever-deteriorating insecurity situation since the enthronement of democracy in 1999. In their expressed opinions, the military were able to control insecurity by taking immediate decisive action any time signs of insecurity occurred. This widespread concern has re-enacted the old debate over which type of government is more permissive and vulnerable to insecurity - authoritarianism or democracy.

Ferreira & Figueiredo (2005) summarised the claims made by proponents of each form of government and demonstrated that proponents of democracy believe that military rule is more susceptible to instability. The authors contended that it violates both due process, basic freedom and rights of citizens thereby driving their complaints and grievances underground only for them to manifest into open armed conflict. On the other hand, democracy according to them, possess weapons to fight insecurity such as respect for basic freedom of citizens, civil rights and due process which allows citizens to openly express their grievances without fear of retribution. They noted, however, that democracy can become vulnerable to insecurity if the practitioners repress innocent civilians and fail to differentiate between non-combatants and terrorist group in its counter-insurgency campaign. Such occurrence, according to them, could provide a fertile condition for use by extremist forces to discredit the government in the eyes of the civil populace thus enhancing their status as champions of the oppressed people which is not a reflection of their true goal.

Opponents of democracy aver that since terrorists normally exploit democratic freedom to commit their crimes, preventing them from abusing such freedom requires that the government should curtail the freedom scope of all citizens (Egbo, 2001; Esetang & Thompson, 2022). Curtailment of the freedom scope of ordinary citizens can only be carried out under an authoritarian military government and not in a democracy as practised in Nigeria. However, in democracy, such punitive measures can be meted out to terrorists alone by subjecting them to extra-democratic measures such as military trial (Court Martial) and indefinite confinement. It is based on this background that we put forward the Guantanamo Bay Detention Camp Approach.

America-Mexico Border Wall Approach: The America-Mexico border wall approach is derived from the border wall project or barriers initiated and implemented by former American president, Donald Trump and constructed along the America-Mexico border. It is a chain of vertical barriers placed along the border to stop unauthorised migrants from entering the US from Mexico. Instead of being a single, continuous structure, the barrier is a discontinuous sequence of physical impediments that go by different names - "wall" or "fences". A "virtual fence" made of sensors, cameras, and other monitoring tools fills the

space between the physical barriers, protecting by alerting security forces, such as border patrol agents, to possible suspected migrant crossings (Felbab-Brown, 2017).

This approach is predicated on the fact the geographical size of Nigeria is very large and its landmass is second in Africa with an area of 941,849 sq. km. Also, Nigeria is centrally located midway between West Africa, East Africa and North Africa sub-regions. This strategic location within Africa is not only attractive to terrorist groups in other parts of Africa owing to its usefulness as an assembly centre but also as the best terrorist launching point to other regions in Africa. Coupled with its porous border which facilitates free cross-border flow of weapons, hard drugs and terrorists from countries sharing borders with Nigeria such as Niger, Chad and Cameroun, this enormous size poses a big problem to the military, police and other security personnel in terms of effective security monitoring and control. Owing also to well-known lack of synergy and cooperation among these security forces and allegation of collusion of some of them with insurgent groups (Omotoso, 2016), it is not safe to wholly depend on security forces to secure the country as s currently prevailing. New strategies must be adopted to complement their efforts and also to check-mate their excesses. It is based on this context that the America-Mexico border wall approach is suggested.

Taking a cue from the America-Mexico border wall initiative, it is strongly suggested that border fences or wall be erected by the federal government around Nigeria's land borders to enhance not only the security of the country but also to halt constant smuggling out of scarce resources of the country. Some Nigeria's political leaders have openly admitted that killer herdsmen who have been killing innocent villagers for years in Benue, Plateau, Kaduna and Taraba States are foreigners. For example, the former governor of Kaduna State, Nasir El Rufai, in 2016 confessed that he sent delegations to fellow Fulani herdsmen who are citizens of Niger, Camerouns, Mali and Senegal for them to stop infiltrating Nigeria to cause violence and killing of Nigerians in Kaduna State (Omotoso, 2016).

Similarly, Sale Bayari, the National Chairman of Gan Allah-Fulani Development Association of Nigeria, confirmed constant entry of foreign killer herdsmen into Nigeria from neighbouring countries. According to him, "ECOWAS protocol allow foreign Fulani to move freely into Nigeria with their cattle and those attacking them or stopping them from grazing their cattle and those attacking them or stopping them from grazing their cattle and those being attacked will not know the difference between the Nigerian herdsmen and the foreign Fulani because they speak the same language and have the same custom and culture" (Alli, 2016, p. 6). To stop such carnage and keep Nigerians safe and secure, barriers must be erected at the Nigerian frontiers. Although the cost of such a project is prohibitive, it is worth undertaking at least in phases over many years in the interest and security of Nigerians.

China Population Growth Control Approach: The Chinese population growth control initiative was a one-child population planning strategy implemented in China between 1976 and 2015 to curb the country's population growth by restricting many families to a single child. It was first preceded by the policy of raising the age of marriage (Jiang.Li and Feldman, 2023). It was later followed by a child spacing policy. When it did not curb population growth a near-universal one-child limit was imposed in 1980 and later enshrined into the country's constitution in 1982. The policy was driven by fears of overpopulation that prevailed in the 1970s. Having achieved their objectives, the Chinese government started to modify the policy gradually starting in 2015 by raising the limit to two children. In May 2021, it was raised to three and in July 2021 all restrictions were removed.

This approach is suggested on the premise that Nigeria has lost control of its population control fight. Such control measures of the government as distribution of contraceptive devices to women, child spacing campaigns, breastfeeding, and condom among others have failed to control rapid population growth in the face of decreasing morbidity and sustained high fertility rate resulting in Nigeria's population growth being rank as one of the highest in the world (Ajala, 2022). According to the latest United Nations data, Nigeria's population is estimated at 228,626,169 (May 2024) based on Worldometer's elaboration. Of the estimated number, only 27.9 million are engaged in productive ventures. The majority of the other unemployed are young people. There is a tendency for these unemployed youths to engage in armed conflict. As asserted by Omale (2013), if there are too many young unemployed persons in the population which Nigeria is unable to provide for, it is a danger signal that insecurity may escalate in future. To reduce the severity of such occurrence, Nigeria should adopt the China-population growth control approach.

Adoption of this approach in Nigeria will enable the country to take effective control of its population growth trajectory with a view to efficient planning and allocation of resources to curb criminality and insecurity. Nigeria may continue to suffer from huge unemployment rate and therefore insecurity if steps are not drastically taken to control Nigeria galloping population growth.

Compulsory Free Education Approach: The usefulness of education to the citizens and the country cannot be over-emphasises. It frees the citizens' minds and enable them to think independently. According to Sen (in Todaro & Smith, 2011):

Education can add to the value of production in the economy and also to the income of the person who has been educated. But even with the same level of income, a person may benefit from education... in being taken more seriously by others (p. 359).

In a similar vein, Ita *et al.* (2018) stressed that all other goals, strategies, and initiatives cannot be implemented successfully without high-quality education. As a result, virtually little progress can be seen from them despite an increase in the number of initiatives and an increase in the money allocated for the implementation of such initiatives. It makes sense that without educated citizens, a rural community cannot support growth. If there are no competent or trainable human resources available in a rural location, businesses - big or small - are not likely to decide to invest there. As a result, education has been the crucial component lacking from Nigeria's efforts to combat insecurity. Without education, citizens will not be able to absorb modern technology and develop their capacity for self-sustaining growth and development.

Notably, countries where citizens suffer from high level of illiteracy are fertile grounds for recruitment for rebel groups (Ukeje, 2003). For certainty, high level of illiteracy is one of the factors that have been exploited by terrorists to gain members into their gangs. It is therefore suggested that government at all levels in Nigeria should collaborate to invest in free compulsory education to all citizens of school age. Its usefulness is that it will not only deny terrorist groups new manpower, it will also enable citizens, especially in the war zones, to take actions concerning themselves based on knowledge and understanding as against being brainwashed by others.

CONCLUSION

This paper set out to appraise the existing approaches adopted by various Nigerian administrations in combating insecurity in the country which include economic approach, military approach and amnesty/appeasement approach. The paper is of the conclusion that although government has invested enormous resources (funds, personnel, time) in combating the insecurity scourge, the monster appears to be unconquerable thereby exposing the weakness of these approaches.

In recent times, countries in the western world which faced similar challenges in the past have diverted from the approaches to new ones, such as Guantanamo Bay detention approach, America-Mexico border wall approach, China population growth control approach and compulsory free education approach. These approaches, if scrupulously executed could finally turn the tide against the terrorist groups in Nigeria. The paper admits that although some of the suggested approaches may be financially costly to the country and may take many years to complete, it is however worth embarking upon in the interest of citizens and survival of the country.

REFERENCES

- Achumba, I. C., Ighomereho, O. S. & Akpor-Robaro, M. O. M. (2013). Security challenges in Nigeria and the implications for business activities and sustainable development. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 4(2), 77-99.
- Ajala, F. (2022). Transitioning Nigeria's national population policy: From policy to implementation. Retrieved from: <http://www.articlesnigeriahealthwatch.com>.
- Ajodo-Adebanjoko, A. (2017). Towards ending conflict and insecurity in the Niger Delta region: A collective non-violent approach. *African Journal on Conflict Resolution*, 17(1), 9-27.
- Ajodo-Adebanjoko, A., & Ugwuoke, O. W. (2014). Poverty and the challenges of insecurity to development. *European Scientific Journal*, 10(14), 361-372.
- Akinwale, A. A (2010). Amnesty and human capital development agenda for the Niger Delta. *Journal of African Studies and Development*, 2(8), 201-207.
- Akowe, T. (2014). Shettima accuses Maku of trivialising Boko Haram. *The Nation*, 11 June.
- Alli, Y. (2016). Rampaging herdsmen were beneficiaries of the Arab Spring. *The Nation*, 28 April. 2016
- Atai, A. J. & Ita, V. E. (2021). Terrorism and global security: An analysis of regional and socio-economic effects on national security. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Sciences*, 5(2), 623-631.
- Atai, A. J., & Esetang, A. (2024). Insecurity in Nigeria: Forms, effects and remedies. *International Journal of Culture and Society*, 2(1), 38-48.
- Austine, E. & Sunday, E. C. (2013). Niger Delta: A critical appraisal of the amnesty programme and social-political development in Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(22), 130-137.
- Beland, D. (2005). The political construction of collective insecurity: From moral panic to blame avoidance and organized irresponsibility. *Centre for European Studies Working Paper Series 126*.
- Egbo, S. (2001). *Political soldiering: Africa's men on horseback*. Enugu: John Jacob's Classic Publishers.

- Esetang, A. & Atai, A. J. (2023). Nigeria and insecurity: Theoretical analysis of internal characteristics and causal factors. *International Journal of Culture and Society, Maiden Edition*, (2), 1-24.
- Esetang, A. & Thompson, E. (2022). Restructuring and devolution of powers: The imperative for democracy and development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advancement in Development Studies* 17(1), 139-149.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999). *Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (As Amended)*. Abuja: Government Printers.
- Felbab-Brown, V. (2017). *President Trump's Border wall*. Washington DC: The Brookings Institution.
- Ferreira, L. V. & Figueiredo, A. (2005). Welfare regimes in the UE 15 and in the enlarged Europe - An exploratory analysis. *45th Congress of the European Regional Science Association: "Land Use and Water Management in a Sustainable Network Society"*, 23-27 August 2005, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, *European Regional Science Association (ERSA), Louvain-la-Neuve*.
- Ibaba, I. S (2011). Amnesty and peace-building in the Niger Delta: Addressing the frustration-aggression trap. *Africana: The Niger Delta (Special Issue)*, 5(1), 238-271.
- Idowu, K. (2018). Security sucks. *The Nation*, 9 July, pp. 3-4.
- Ita, V. E. & Bassey, J. E. (2022). Rising youth unemployment and the socio-economic realities in Nigeria: The Akwa Ibom State experience. *International Journal of Development and Economic Sustainability*, 10(3), 1-14.
- Ita, V. E. (2022). Tackling terrorists' activities: Nigeria's Boko Haram and Syria's ISIS in comparative perspective. *AKSU Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(1), 28-38.
- Ita, V. E., Edet, L. I. & Effiong, J. E. (2018). Towards sustainable poverty reduction in Nigeria: Comparative benefits and the necessity of education option. *Asian Journal of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities*, 6(1), 27-44.
- Jackson, R. & Sorensen, S. (2003). *Introduction to international relations: Theories and approaches*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Jiang, O., Li, S. & Feldman, M. W. (2013). China's population policy at the crossroads: Social impacts and prospects. [*Asian Journal of Social Science*, 41\(2\), 193-218.](#)
- Kegley, C. W. & Blanton, S. L. (2011). *World politics: Trend and transformation*. Boston: Wadsworth.
- Ndiyo, N. (2005). *Fundamentals of research in behavioural sciences and humanities*. Calabar: WUSE Publishers.
- Ojo, J. (2018). Nigeria politics, economy and security in 2018. *The Punch*, 26 December.
- Oluwaniyi, O. O. (2011). Post amnesty programme in the Niger Delta: Challenges and prospects. *Conflict Trends*, 4, 46-54.
- Omale, D. J. (2013). Terrorism and counter-terrorism in Nigeria: Theoretical paradigms and lessons for public policy. *Canadian Social Science*, 9(3), 96-103.
- Omeihe, E. (2018). Yari's frustration. *The Nation*, 25 June.
- Omotoso, G. (2016). Paying the enemy. *The Nation*, 8 December.
- Omotoso, G. (2017). 43 repentant insurgents for de-radicalisation. *The Nation*, 24 July.
- Onifade, C. A., Imhonopi, D. & Urim, U. M. (2013). Addressing the insecurity challenge in Nigeria: The imperative of moral values and virtue ethics. *Global Journal of Human Social Science Political Science*, 13(2), 53-63.

- Raji, A. A. & Yusuf, A. T. (2024). Niger Delta and the challenge of Nigeria's national security. *Journal of Political Discourse*, 2(2), 61-76.
- Todaro, M. & Smith, S. (2011). *Economic development*. London: Pearson Education Limited.
- Tunoh, B. (2021, 30 April). Army renames northeast's Operation Lafiya Dole. Retrieved from <https://www.channelstv.com/2021/04/30/army-renames-northeast-operation-lafiya-dole/>
- Ukeje, C. (2003). Sierra Leone: The long descent into civil war. In Sesay, A. (Ed.), *Civil wars, child soldiers and post-conflict peacebuilding in West Africa*. Lagos: College Press and Publishers.
- United Nations (2024). World Population Prospects: The 2022 Revision. New York: United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division.
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (1994). *Human development report*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- William, P. D. (2008). *Security Studies: An Introduction*. New York: Routledge.
- Zubairu, N. (2020). Rising insecurity in Nigeria: Causes and solution. *Journal of Studies in Social Sciences*, 19(4), 1-11.